

EFFECT OF PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL METHODS ON EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY IN PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS IN RWANDA, A CASE STUDY OF RWAND AIRSingh Satyendra Narayan¹ and Ms Yvonne Gatsinzi²¹Professor, University of Kigali²University of Kigali**ABSTRACT**

Performance management has been gaining momentum both in private and public sectors. Performance appraisal which is part of performance management, refers to the process that evaluates the performance of employees at work in relation to the task or project the employee has worked upon. It is an evaluation of the contribution of employees towards the performance of organizations. The main objective of the research was to investigate the effect of performance appraisal methods on the employee productivity in public institutions in Rwanda, taking a case of Rwandair. The specific objectives included, to investigate the relationship between results-based management performance appraisal method and employee productivity in Rwandair; to determine the effect of assessment centre performance appraisal method on employee productivity Rwandair and to establish the relationship between 360-Degree feedback performance appraisal method and employee productivity Rwandair. Descriptive research design as well as correlation design were used to achieve these objectives. A sample size of 119 respondents were selected using stratified random sampling technique. Data was collected using structured questionnaire. The data collected was analysed using SPSS version 21 and presented using tables and graphs. Pearson's coefficient correlation and regression analysis were also conducted to determine the relationship among the study variables. The findings on objective one showed that 74.4% of the respondents said that they were aware of appraisal methods used in evaluating employee performance in Rwandair. A total of 97.7% of respondents agreed that the result-based management has made everyone accountable in their office of work. The findings on objective two revealed that all the agreed that continuous evaluation of the employee progress ensures that the employee appraisal is detailed. All respondents were also in agreement about the statement that the performance appraisal help the management to increase the productivity of the employees. All the three indicators of the independent variable, namely, result based management, assessment centre method and 360-degree method, are positively and significantly related to the dependent variable, employee productivity. The regression model was found to be significant ($F = 34.87, p = 0.000$) with an R-squared of 0.549. This showed that the combined effect of the three performance appraisal methods influences 54.9% of the employee productivity at Rwandair. The results revealed that all the three indicator variables were significant at 5% are presented. The researcher highly recommends that Rwandair and other organizations should have effective employee appraisal methods if they are to keep their employees motivated. The researcher also recommends that employees should be collaborative with the management during the appraisal process in order to help obtain the best output about their performance.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Performance management has been gaining momentum both in private and public sectors. According to Armstrong M. (2022) performance management (PM) is a process that is goal-oriented and which is direct towards ensuring that organizational processes are in place to maximize the productivity of employees, teams and ultimately the productivity of organization. It is a system that aims to develop individuals with commitment and needed competence with the target set on achieving the strategic goals of the organization. One of the main elements in the performance management is performance appraisal (PA). performance appraisal refers to the process that evaluates the performance of employees at work in relation to the task or project the employee has worked upon. It is an evaluation of the contribution of employees towards the performance of organizations. The chief objective of performance appraisal methods is to help organization to identify employees worth and contribution to the company. Performance appraisal methods do provide organizations with opportunities to identify areas of strength of the workforce as well as improving the workforce where needed. Performance appraisals can benefit both the employees and organizations by clarifying goals and expectations. They help to create and improve a conversational atmosphere between management and the employees (Snell, S., Bohlander G.W. & Morris, S., 2015).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The overall performance of an organization is hinged on the productivity of its employees. Various research have highlighted the crucial role and the importance of human resource in all the organizations regardless of their industry. Moreover, it is the human who formulate organizational goals and strategies and turn them in to actions. Therefore the role played by each and every employee's productivity can never be overemphasised.

However, the productivity of employees usually fluctuate and can negatively influence the organization performance. The reason could be the failure of organization and management equitably and sufficiently motivating the employees. In order for organization to achieve equitable motivational strategies, there is need for effective appraisal methods which in turn would increase the productivity of the employees. The government of Rwanda has been at the forefront in campaigning for employees' productivity especially in the government institutions through various mechanisms like the performance contracting and through programmes.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH-

The research was guided by three specific objectives as stated below:

1. To investigate the relationship between results-based management performance appraisal method and employee productivity in Rwandair.
2. To determine the effect of assessment centre performance appraisal method on employee productivity Rwandair.
3. To establish the relationship between 360-Degree feedback performance appraisal method and employee productivity Rwandair.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Is there a relationship between results-based management performance appraisal method and employee productivity Rwandair?
2. What is the effect of assessment centre performance appraisal method on employee productivity Rwandair?
3. What is the relationship between 360-Degree feedback performance appraisal method and employee productivity Rwandair

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature

Performance Appraisal Methods

According to A. and Rabenu E. (2018), performance appraisal system refers to the development of individuals with competence and commitment, working towards the achievement of shared meaningful objectives within an organization which supports and encourages their achievement. The system gauges the performance of the employees based on a given rating scale or based on the goals that had being pre-set before the task. It also gauges the performance of an employee vis-à-vis a task or project assigned to the employee. It therefore act as feedback system aimed at finding the contribution of an employee to the overall organization performance.

360-Degree Appraisal Method

According to Hailey J. and Sorgenfrei M. (2004), 360-degree appraisal method is a systematic collection and feedback of performance data on individuals or groups derived from a number of stakeholders on their performance. The stakeholders involve the crucial people who have interest in the outcome of the organization and therefore of the individual actions of the employees. As such, 360-degree appraisal method is a popular PAM which involves evaluating performance of an individual or team from multiple level within the organization and even from external sources. In this method therefore, evaluation is done by various parties including the senior, junior, the employee himself or herself, peers, team members and customers.

The 360-degree appraisal method has therefore five key parties involved in the appraising the employee performance as shown below

Performance Appraisal Methods and Employee Productivity

Performance appraisal system is seen as a tool for measuring employees’ productivity against a set standard of measures. The objective of such measurements is to ensure that the employees are aware of the level of performance, their contribution to the organization and the areas they need to improve their productivity. Hence, apart from aiming to achieve the overall goals of the organizations, PAMs aim at improving productivity levels of individual employees. However, as noted by Finney M. and Robbins S.P. (2013) the measures that are set to gauge employees performance should be appropriate to the organizational needs or objectives, should be clear and not confusing and consistent. This will be then the bases for encouraging and motivating employees to be high achievers.

Conceptual Framework

Independent Variable:

Dependent Variable:

Performance Appraisal Methods

Employee Productivity

Conceptual Framework

As shown in Figure the research was guided by two variables, namely the independent variable and the dependent variable. On one side of the figure is the performance appraisal methods as the independent variable. The appraisal method in this research include result base management, assessment centre method and 360-

degree feedback method. As discussed in theoretical literature, there is no one single method that is the best for all organization. In addition, organizations should try to blend different methods for the appraisal to be more effective. In this research, the results based method proposed ‘what’ is being evaluated, the assessment centre method proposed ‘when’ is the evaluation to be carried out while the 360-degree method proposed ‘who’ should carry out the evaluation.

On the other hand, the dependent variable was the employee productivity which is indicated by task completion, timely customer service and less absenteeism reports for the employee

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

Research Design

Research design refers to the way the entire study is carried out including the data collection and analysis (Mugenda O. & Mugenda, O. 2003). The research design provides an overall plan that guides the conduct of the entire research work. In this research, descriptive research design was used to respond to the research questions and providing a description of the phenomenon being investigated. In addition, the researcher used correlational research design to determine the relationship between the study variable. The research was therefore quantitative in nature involving numerical data analysis.

Study Population

According to Kothari C.R. (2003), population refers to the set of all elements or items in research. The current study was carried out in Rwandair and involved the staff working in the organization at the head office. The total number of employees are 169 as shown as follows

Table 3.1: Study population

Department	Number of employees
Commercial	77
Finance	35
Human Resource	5
Support Services (FSS)	52
Total	169

Source: HRM Department, 2024

Sample Size

According to Mugenda O. and Mugenda O. (2003), it is only justifiable to select a sample if the population is more than 100. In this case, Yamane (1967) formula was used to determine the sample size as given in the following formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the target population and e the margin of error which is 0.05.

Therefore, $n = \frac{160}{1+169*0.05^2} \approx 119$

3.4.2 Sampling Technique

According to Creswell J.W. and Creswell J.D. (2017), sampling techniques refer to methods used in selecting the sample items from a population. There are various methods that a researcher can use, but these can be grouped into two, namely, probabilistic or non-probabilistic. In this research, stratified random sampling technique was used to select the respondents.

Sample Size for each Department

Department	Number of employees	Proportion	Sample
Commercial	77	0.46	54
Finance	35	0.21	25
Human Resource	5	0.03	4
Support Services (FSS)	52	0.31	37
Total	169		119

Data Collection Methods and Tools

According to Kothari C.R. (2003), data can either be primary or secondary. As far as this research is concerned, only primary data will be used. Primary data was collected through the use of questionnaires submitted through

Google forms to the selected respondents thereafter filled questionnaires were collected for analysis and interpretations. The questionnaires was divided in to three sections, A, B and C. Section A was concerned with gathering the background information on the respondents, Section B collected data related to the specific objectives and therefore divided in to three subsections according to the specific objectives while Section C collected data on employee productivity.

DATA ANALYSIS,

Distribution of Gender-

This section dealt with the background of the respondents which included gender, age, working experience, highest achieved education and the job office of the respondents

Distribution of respondents by gender

Above Fig shows that the female and male eventually equally distributed among the accessed respondents.

The age group of the respondents

Age group	Frequency	Percent
Below 26 years	2	2.2
26-30yrs	11	12.2
31-35yrs	37	41.1
36-40yrs	26	28.9
41-45yrs	3	3.3
Above 46	11	12.2
Total	90	100.0

With respect to the age group of the respondents, Table 4above table presents the results obtained from the field. As shown, majority of the respondents, that is, 41.1% were in the age group between 31-35 years. This was followed by those respondents age between 36-40 years as presented by 28.9%. Both 26-30 years and above 46 years age groups had similar representation of 12.2% of the respondents. The lowest age group presented by 2.2% was in the age below 26 years.

Working experience of the respondents

Time (in years)	Frequency	Percent
1-2yrs	7	7.8
3-5yrs	46	51.1
5-10yrs	32	35.6
Above 10yrs	5	5.6
Total	90	100.0

The background information was also concerned with the working experience of the respondents in Rwandair as measured in years. Above table shows that 51.1% of the respondents had spent between 3-5 years followed by those who had spent between 5-10 years at 35.6%. 7.8% of the respondents were between 1-2 years while 5.6% were above 10 years.

Levels of Education

As shown in Figure most of the respondents as represented by 67.78% had a bachelor degree followed by 26.67% of the respondents who had master degree. The rest, 5.6% indicated they had certificate. This clearly shows that most of the respondents were highly educated to provide quality information in relation to the research objectives.

Distribution of the respondents according to their office/department

Figure 4.3 shows that 33.33% of the respondents were in supportive services office followed closely by those who were in commercial services at 32.22%. Those respondents in the finance department were represented by 21.11% while those in human were 12.22% and the remaining 1.11% were in the marketing department. The results clearly showed that different departments were represented in the sample selected.

Findings on Objective One

The first objective was more centred on investigating the relationship between results based management appraisal and employee productivity in Rwandair. To achieve the objective, the respondents were given closed-ended questions rated with a five-point Likert scale where 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree and 5=strongly agree.

On Respondents' Awareness

Statement		n	%
1.Are you aware of the appraisal methods used in evaluating employee performance in Rwandair.?	Yes	67	74.4%
	Not Sure	20	22.2%
	No	3	3.3%
2.Have you at any time been involved in evaluating you fellow employees	Yes	61	67.8%
	Not Sure	21	23.3%
	No	8	8.9%

Respondents' views on the sense of ownership

	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev
3.Rwandair always involves its employees in formulating targets, objects and the desired results on a regular basis	1	1.1%	5	5.6%	0	0.0%	58	64.4%	26	28.9%	4.14	.77
4.The level of involvement has created a sense of ownership in the employees	0	0.0%	5	5.6%	0	0.0%	59	65.6%	26	28.9%	4.18	.70
5.I work so hard knowing that the results I achieve will benefit all of us	1	1.1%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	56	62.2%	32	35.6%	4.30	.64

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Respondents' views on accountability

Statements	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev		
6.The appraisal of employees within Rwandair is carried out in an accountable manner	0	0.0%	2	2.2%	0	0.0%	54	60.0%	34	37.8%	4.33	.60
7.Every employee in Rwandair is aware of his/her duties and responsibilities	2	2.2%	1	1.1%	5	5.6%	29	32.2%	53	58.9%	4.44	.84
8.The result based management has ensured that everyone is held accountable in their office of work	0	0.0%	2	2.2%	0	0.0%	66	73.3%	22	24.4%	4.20	.55

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Respondents' views on transparency

	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev		
9.The evaluation of employees performance is conducted in a transparent manner	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	68	75.6%	22	24.4%	4.24	.43
10.All the employees are aware of the evaluation process and the framework of evaluation	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	54	60.0%	36	40.0%	4.40	.49
11.The evaluation of employees has increased the level of transparency in the organization	0	0.0%	2	2.2%	16	17.8%	46	51.1%	26	28.9%	4.07	.75

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Findings on Objective Two

The second objective in this dissertation was to investigate the effect of assessment centre performance appraisal method on employee productivity in Rwandair. The respondents were given structured questionnaire with five point Likert scale statements where 5=strongly agree, 4=agree, 3=neutral, 2=disagree and 1=strongly disagree. The main indicators used included pre-assessment, during assessment and post assessment. The results from the field are presented in the tables that follow.

Respondents' views on employee pre-assessment

	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev
12.Rwandair conducts different assessment of its employees based on the level of progress	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	65	72.2%	25	27.8%	4.28	.45
13.Pre-assessment ensures that the employees are aware of their responsibilities	0	0.0%	2	2.2%	15	16.7%	50	55.6%	23	25.6%	4.04	.72
14.Pre-assessment is a moment to prepare us to achieve the desired results	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	56	62.2%	34	37.8%	4.38	.49

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Respondents' views on during assessment

	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev
15.Continuous evaluation of the employee progress ensures that appraisal is detailed	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	59	65.6%	31	34.4%	4.34	.48
16.Assessment during the work is much more effective	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	51	56.7%	39	43.3%	4.43	.50
17.Most employees are present at their workplace during evaluation	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	50	55.6%	40	44.4%	4.44	.50

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Table 4.1: Respondents’ views on post assessment

	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev
18.The management always collect feedback after the evaluation of employees in Rwandair	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	5	63.3%	3	35.6%	4.33	.54
19.The organization always shares and communicate the feedback with employees in a friendly manner	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	4	54.4%	4	45.6%	4.46	.50
20.Further training and career development in the organization are based on the evaluation feedback	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	5	55.6%	3	43.3%	4.41	.56

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Findings on Objective Three

The last objective in this dissertation was to establish the relationship between 360-Degree feedback performance appraisal method and employee productivity. The main factors selected as indicators of the 360-degree performance method included self-assessment, peer review and management review. To be able to measure these variables five point Likert scale was used with 5=strongly agree, 4=agree, 3=neutral, 2=disagree and 1=strongly disagree.

Respondents’ views on self-assessment

	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev
21.Rwandair provides chance for its employees to assess their own performance	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	6	67.8%	2	31.1%	4.29	.53
22.Most of the employees assess their performance objectively	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	5	57.8%	3	41.1%	4.39	.56
23.Self-assessment is important for us because the management consider it in the overall appraisal	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	6	66.7%	3	33.3%	4.33	.47

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Respondents’ views on peer review

	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev
24.We usually evaluate the work of our colleagues	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	5	56.7%	3	43.3%	4.43	.50
25.Peer reviews help improve team work among the employees	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	4	48.9%	4	51.1%	4.51	.50
26.All employees are fair enough in evaluating their colleagues	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	5	58.9%	3	41.1%	4.41	.50

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Respondents’ views on management review

	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev
27.Employees are also evaluated by their senior managers	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	5	58.9%	3	40.0%	4.38	.55
28.Evaluation of employees by the management is also important in providing manager first hand report	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	4	53.3%	4	46.7%	4.47	.50
29.Management evaluations are conducted in a fair manner	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	4	54.4%	4	44.4%	4.42	.56

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Respondents' views on employees' productivity

Statement	SD		D		N		A		SA			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean	Stdev		
30.Capacity building and training of employees is based on past appraisal results	0	0.0%	3	3.3%	0	0.0%	55	61.1%	32	35.6%	4.29	.64
31.Performance appraisal help the management to increase the productivity of the employees	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	56	62.2%	33	36.7%	4.34	.54
32.It reveal the strength and weakness of individuals for training and development in future	0	0.0%	2	2.2%	0	0.0%	52	57.8%	36	40.0%	4.36	.61
33.The performance appraisal helps me to complete my tasks on time	0	0.0%	2	2.2%	0	0.0%	48	53.3%	40	44.4%	4.40	.61
34.Majority of employees have improved their work performance owing to management evaluation	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	52	57.8%	37	41.1%	4.39	.56
35.Customer service delivery has improved in the organization due to performance appraisal	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	50	55.6%	40	44.4%	4.44	.50
36.Customers are now more satisfied with the service delivery	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	55	61.1%	35	38.9%	4.39	.49
37.Most workers are always at their workplace on time and throughout the work hours	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	52	57.8%	38	42.2%	4.42	.50
38.Performance appraisal has reduced the rate of absenteeism in the organization	0	0.0%	1	1.1%	0	0.0%	53	58.9%	36	40.0%	4.38	.55

SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, N=Neutral, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree, Stdev=Standard deviation

Correlation matrix

		Employee Productivity	Result based	Assessment centre	360-Degree
Employee Productivity	Pearson Correlation	1	.619**	.480**	.392**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	90	90	90	90
Result based	Pearson Correlation	.619**	1	.214*	.183
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.043	.084
	N	90	90	90	90
Assessment centre	Pearson Correlation	.480**	.214*	1	.286**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.043		.006
	N	90	90	90	90
360-Degree	Pearson Correlation	.392**	.183	.286**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.084	.006	
	N	90	90	90	90

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Regression model and ANOVA table

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.741 ^a	.549	.533	.13453

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	1.893	3	.631	34.870	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.556	86	.018		
	Total	3.449	89			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Productivity
 b. Predictors: (Constant), 360-Degree, Result based, Assessment centre

Regression Coefficients Table

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

1	(Constant)	.697	.399		1.747	.084
	Result based	.330	.048	.514	6.875	.000
	Assessment centre	.326	.081	.310	4.046	.000
	360-Degree	.186	.068	.209	2.740	.007
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Productivity						

CONCLUSION

The findings obtained from the field through structured questionnaire. For the first objective, the findings have revealed that result based management is a key contributing factor to performance appraisal and influences the employees productivity. This conclusion was drawn from the high level of agreement among the contacted respondents on the effect that result based appraisal has on their work life. In addition, majority of the respondents were in agreement that result based management increases the sense of ownership, accountability and transparency of the employees. These findings are in line with previous findings from other authors like Masenya, et al., (2018); Mone, et al. (2018) and Rudani (2020).

In relation to the second objective, this dissertation has found that assessment centre performance appraisal, especially when conducting at the work station of an employee is important factor within an organization. The findings revealed that majority of the respondents agreed that such assessments, including pre-assessment, during assessment and post assessment ensures that the employee performance appraisal is an ongoing activity. On the third objective, the researcher concluded that the 360-degree performance appraisal method provides an all-round appraisal of the employee. This was informed by the responses obtained where majority of the respondents indicated that different performance appraisal carried out by different people help to capture different areas of employee performance.

Further, correlation and regression analysis conducted in this dissertation pointed out the significant relationship that the three forms of performance appraisal have on the employee productivity. All of these were found to be positive and significantly related to productivity of the employee. Moreover, the regression analysis should that the model was significant with the three have a positive and significant combined effect. The findings are contrary to the findings by Rahahleh, et al. (2019) who found negative effect of establishing performance appraisal methods on the performance of employees. However, some other authors (such as Olabode, et al. 2013; Bekele, et al. 2014; Mbabazi & Shukla, 2015; Agyare, et al. 2016) found positive and significant effect of performance appraisal on the employee productivity at workplace.

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